

1 **Fingerprints for early detection of changes in the AMOC**

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ABSTRACT

6 Different strategies have been proposed in previous studies for monitoring
7 the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC). As well as arrays
8 to directly monitor the AMOC strength, various fingerprints have been
9 suggested to represent an aspect of the AMOC based on properties, such
10 as temperature and density. The additional value of fingerprints potentially
11 includes: the ability to detect a change earlier than a change in the AMOC
12 itself; the ability to extend a timeseries back into the past; the ability to detect
13 crossing a threshold.

14
15 In this study we select metrics that have been proposed as fingerprints
16 in previous studies and evaluate their ability to detect AMOC changes in a
17 number of scenarios (internal variability, weakening from increased green-
18 house gases, weakening from hosing and hysteresis) in the eddy-permitting
19 coupled climate model HadGEM3-GC2. We find that the metrics that
20 perform best are the temperature metrics based on large scale differences, the
21 large scale meridional density gradient, and the vertical density difference
22 in the Labrador Sea. The best metric for monitoring the AMOC depends
23 somewhat on the processes driving the change. Hence the best strategy would
24 be to consider multiple fingerprints to provide early detection of all likely
25 AMOC changes.

26 **1. Introduction**

27 The Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) transports large amounts of heat in
28 the Atlantic significantly influencing the climate. Much evidence has been seen of the potential
29 impacts of changes in the AMOC on climate, whether it is from interannual-decadal variability
30 (Knight et al. 2006; Hermanson et al. 2014), a gradual weakening of the AMOC from increased
31 greenhouse gases (Woollings et al. 2012; Drijfhout et al. 2012; Haarsma et al. 2015), or a more
32 rapid collapse of the AMOC (Jackson et al. 2015). Hence there is strong need to monitor the
33 AMOC, and if possible provide early warning of any changes.

34 Currently there are observational programs continuously monitoring the AMOC in the subtrop-
35 ical North Atlantic (RAPID-MOCHA, McCarthy et al. (2015b)) and the subpolar North Atlantic
36 (OSNAP, Lozier et al. (2019)), with other programs providing limited observations at other lat-
37 itudes in the Atlantic (McCarthy et al. 2019; Frajka-Williams et al. 2019). Results so far show
38 large variability on many timescales meaning that a much longer timeseries is required to detect
39 an AMOC trend (Baehr et al. 2007; Roberts and Palmer 2012).

40 An alternative way to monitor the AMOC is via metrics that can be used as an AMOC finger-
41 print (defined here to be a metric which well represents an aspect of the AMOC). Many studies
42 have suggested metrics that can be used as a fingerprint of the AMOC. These can be used to en-
43 able historical reconstructions, such as in the studies of (Rahmstorf et al. 2015; Caesar et al. 2018;
44 Thornalley et al. 2018). Some have been suggested as ways to improve near-term predictions of
45 the AMOC or its impacts (Hermanson et al. 2014; Sévellec et al. 2018) or to reconstruct multi-
46 decadal variability (Zhang 2008; Msadek et al. 2010; Roberts et al. 2013a). Others have developed
47 fingerprints to detect a weakening of the AMOC (Baehr et al. 2007; Roberts et al. 2013a; Vellinga
48 and Wood 2004). Some of these may provide faster detection of a change, either through the

49 fingerprint having less high frequency variability than the AMOC (greater signal-to-noise ratio,
50 (Baehr et al. 2007; Brennan et al. 2008; Roberts and Palmer 2012)), or even being a precursor
51 to an AMOC change, such as changes in deep convection regions found to lead AMOC changes
52 (Ba et al. 2014; Danabasoglu et al. 2016). A useful fingerprint should satisfy three criteria: firstly
53 be a good representation of an aspect of the AMOC that we want to monitor; secondly that the
54 relationship with the AMOC should be understood physically; and thirdly that it must be poten-
55 tially observable. For early warning, the fingerprint must also be able to detect a change in the
56 AMOC before it is detected by the AMOC itself. Most metrics that have been proposed are based
57 on ocean temperatures (Latif et al. 2004; Zhang 2008; Msadek et al. 2010; Roberts et al. 2013a;
58 Zhang and Zhang 2015; Caesar et al. 2018), since changes in the heat transported by the AMOC
59 are likely to affect temperatures in the North Atlantic, or densities (Baehr et al. 2007; Roberts et al.
60 2013a; Hermanson et al. 2014; Butler et al. 2016; Robson et al. 2016; Haskins et al. 2019), since
61 there are arguments associating the AMOC with density or pressure gradients (Butler et al. 2016).
62 Metrics of mixed layer depth (MLD) that indicate convection were proposed by Jackson and Wood
63 (2018a), and gradients in sea level which can indicate volume transport in the Gulf Stream have
64 also been proposed (Bingham and Hughes 2009; McCarthy et al. 2015a). Transports of freshwater
65 at the south of the Atlantic (de Vries and Weber 2005) and in the subtropical Atlantic (Mecking
66 et al. 2016; Jackson and Wood 2018a) have been suggested as potential indicators of an AMOC
67 collapse. Some studies have looked for multi-variate fingerprints based on water mass properties
68 (Vellinga and Wood 2004; Roberts and Palmer 2012; Klus et al. 2018) though Roberts and Palmer
69 (2012) warned against simply using statistical techniques to look for patterns, without investigat-
70 ing the physical relationships. Various studies have highlighted the added value of considering a
71 number of different metrics (Vellinga and Wood 2004; Roberts and Palmer 2012; Klus et al. 2018),

72 including different locations of the AMOC to assess spatial coherence (Bingham et al. 2007; Feng
73 et al. 2014).

74 In this study we will test various metrics that have previously been proposed as AMOC finger-
75 prints. We will use an eddy-permitting coupled climate model to test candidate metrics for detect-
76 ing AMOC change in different scenarios: internal variability, changes from an AMOC weakening
77 (forced by an increase in greenhouse gases or addition of freshwater), and the recovery after a
78 weakening.

79 There are good arguments that what we should be monitoring is not the AMOC itself, but the
80 total Atlantic ocean heat transport (AOHT), which is dependent on changes in the horizontal circu-
81 lation as well as changes in ocean temperature. It is changes in the heat transport that have impacts
82 on the ocean temperatures and hence on the climate. However studies proposing fingerprints for
83 monitoring have developed these fingerprints for the AMOC, so we focus this study on testing the
84 metrics against the AMOC itself. We note that when changes in the AMOC are large, there are
85 also large changes in heat transport and hence the metrics are both fingerprints of the AMOC and
86 AOHT. For smaller changes, in particular for studying variability, we examine the potential of the
87 metrics to be fingerprints of both the AMOC and AOHT.

88 Although some of the experiments used here have been found to have a threshold beyond which
89 the AMOC does not recover when freshwater is added (Jackson and Wood 2018a), we will not be
90 covering the use of the timeseries statistics to indicate the approach of a threshold. Various papers
91 (Lenton 2011; Lenton et al. 2012; Boulton et al. 2014; Nikolaou et al. 2015; Klus et al. 2018) have
92 shown that this is potentially a useful indicator of approaching a threshold. However, although
93 current techniques have been shown to indicate approaching a threshold (through increased vari-
94 ance or autocorrelation), they do not indicate how far away the threshold is. The usefulness of
95 timeseries statistics in the real world is also constrained by the need to have a reliable fingerprint

96 with a long (hundreds of years) timeseries. For the experiments considered in this paper where
97 changes are occurring quickly and the lengths of integrations are short, it is difficult to explore the
98 statistics.

99 This paper is structured as follows. Section 2 describes the model, experiments used and AMOC
100 response, and section 3 introduces the different metrics. Then we examine the potential of the
101 metrics as AMOC fingerprint for variability in section 4, for AMOC weakening in section 5, to
102 distinguish an AMOC recovery in section 6 and to detect a threshold in section 7. Finally, in
103 section 8, we present our conclusions.

104 **2. Models and experiments**

105 *a. Model description*

106 In this analysis we use the eddy-permitting, coupled climate model HadGEM3-GC2 which is
107 the forerunner to HadGEM3-GC3.1 submitted to the 6th Coupled Model Intercomparison Project
108 (CMIP6). The GCM consists of ocean, atmosphere, land and sea-ice components and is described
109 in detail in Williams et al. (2015). In particular the ocean model component uses the G05 version
110 (Megann et al. 2014) of the NEMO model (Madec 2008), with a nominal resolution of 0.25° and
111 75 vertical levels.

112 *b. Experiments*

113 We make use of a long control run (200 years) with preindustrial forcings (CON) and a 140 year
114 long run which is spun off where the CO_2 concentrations are increased at 1% per year up to 4
115 times preindustrial concentrations (1PC). We also use a suite of experiments where an idealized
116 additional flux of freshwater (hosing) is added to the North Atlantic north of 50°N . See Jackson and
117 Wood (2018b) for details. These experiments are referred to as hos01, hos02, hos03, hos05, hos10

118 where the numbers indicate the amount of hosing added (0.1-1.0 Sv; 1 Sv= 10^6 m³/s). Finally,
119 experiments are spun off from these where the hosing is stopped after a length of time T . In some
120 of these the AMOC recovers back to its control strength, but in others the AMOC stays weak.
121 These experiments are described in Jackson and Wood (2018a) and are referred to as off H_T for
122 those where the hosing H is applied for T years (ie off05_20 has had a hosing of 0.5Sv for 20
123 years).

124 *c. The AMOC*

125 The AMOC streamfunction in CON shows a coherent overturning cell (Fig 1a). M26 and M45
126 are the strengths at 26.5°N and 45°N (measured as the maximum over depth) which have means
127 of 14.5Sv and 11.6Sv respectively, and annual standard deviations of 0.9Sv and 1.0Sv (Fig 2). The
128 AOHT (maximum over latitude of the Atlantic ocean heat transport) has a mean value of 0.99PW
129 with an annual standard deviation of 0.07PW (Fig 1d). Timeseries show coherent multidecadal
130 variability (Fig 1e), with AOHT instantaneously varying with M26 and M45 leading by a couple
131 of years (Fig 1f). A lag between M26 and M45 is consistent with other studies showing AMOC
132 signals propagating from high to low latitudes in the North Atlantic (Xu et al. 2019).

133 In the 1PC experiment there is a substantial weakening of AMOC, including at 26.5°N and
134 45°N, and this weakens the AOHT (Fig 1c,d). In the hosing experiments, the freshening of the
135 North Atlantic also weakens the AMOC and AOHT (Fig 1b,d). When hosing stops, the AMOC
136 recovers in some experiments and not others (Fig 2). There are significant correlations between
137 M26 and M45 and AOHT for all experiments since when the AMOC change is large, it is coherent
138 across the basin and has a large impact on the heat transport. Hence results for many sections of
139 this study are at least qualitatively similar when using M45 or AOHT rather than M26 (not shown).
140 However there are some differences when using fingerprints to detect variability (section 4). This

141 is because internal variability can differ between the subtropical and subpolar AMOC and because
142 we might expect variability in temperature or the horizontal circulation to influence AOHT as well
143 as the AMOC. Hence we include some discussion of the potential of the metrics to be fingerprints
144 of M45 and AOHT in section 4.

145 **3. Metrics**

146 We start with a description of different metrics (listed in Table 1 and shown in Fig 3 and 4),
147 and a comparison with the AMOC. Later sections investigate the potential of these metrics as
148 fingerprints for different scenarios.

149 Figures for a few of the metrics are shown in Fig 5-8 and correlations of decadal mean timeseries
150 of metrics with M26 for the different experiments are shown in Table 2. Many metrics show strong
151 correlations for the 1PC experiment and the hosing experiments, however in these experiments
152 many quantities have long term trends and this strong correlation just means that the metric also
153 has a trend.

154 *a. Existing monitoring arrays*

155 We extract the AMOC in a similar way to two existing observational arrays. For the RAPID
156 section we calculate the AMOC at 26.5°N using the observational method of geostrophic approx-
157 imations to velocity, rather than model velocities themselves (Roberts et al. 2013b). Hence there
158 are slight differences with M26, though, as expected, there are very high correlations. The RAPID
159 observations have three components: the Florida Straits transport (FC), the upper mid ocean com-
160 ponent (UMO) and the wind-driven Ekman component (McCarthy et al. 2015b). The latter of
161 these is very strongly related to the wind forcing and has little relationship to the AMOC, so is
162 excluded. Much of the AMOC weakening in the hosing and 1PC runs comes from the FC compo-

163 nent rather than the UMO component, however we note that individually both components show
164 little simultaneous relationship to M26 during decadal variability in the control (Table 2).

165 The OSNAP section (Lozier et al. 2019) is calculated from model velocities in density coor-
166 dinates and is extracted along the observational path using the method in Zou et al. (2019). The
167 OSNAP overturning and its east and west components shows strong correlations with the M26
168 (Table 2), however the east component has the strongest mean strength and greatest weakening in
169 the 1% and hosing experiments (not shown).

170 *b. Temperature metrics*

171 Many metrics have been calculated based on sea surface temperature (SST) because SST can be
172 strongly impacted by the heat transport of the AMOC. Temperatures are also readily measured,
173 through satellite data at the surface, through subsurface ARGO floats and even indirectly through
174 paleo evidence (Mann et al. 2008). The metrics shown differ in the locations used for the metric
175 (see Table 1 and Fig 3). Various studies have shown links in models between the multidecadal
176 variability of Atlantic surface temperatures and multidecadal variability of the AMOC, leading
177 (Latif et al. 2004; Msadek et al. 2010; Roberts et al. 2013a; Rahmstorf et al. 2015) to propose
178 indices (amv1, amv2, SST_dipole, SST_spg) based on the SST in the North Atlantic. To remove
179 the influence of temperature changes from increasing greenhouse gases these indices also subtract
180 either the global mean, the hemispheric mean or South Atlantic mean temperature. Caesar et al.
181 (2018) instead used a dipole between the Gulf Stream and subpolar gyre and only winter and
182 spring SSTs.

183 Of the SST metrics, amv2 (Fig 5) has the strongest relationship with M26, though amv1 and
184 SST_spg also generally have strong correlations. Some (SST_dipole, see Fig 6, and SST.caesar)
185 show little relationship with M26 in the control, however if temperature changes are caused by the

186 AMOC changing heat transport which changes the heat content, then a lagged relationship would
187 be expected instead. This will be investigated further in section 4. Most temperature metrics show
188 strong correlations when there are large ongoing trends (1% and hosing experiments), although
189 are less good at explaining the recovery experiments. SST_dipole shows a negative trend for 1PC
190 because, although the subpolar gyre warms less than other regions, as expected, the Nordic seas
191 further north warms more (Fig 3).

192 Similar to SST fingerprints, Zhang and Zhang (2015) suggested using empirical orthogonal func-
193 tion (EOF) of detrended heat content over the top 700m (uohc) or temperatures at 400m (Tsub).
194 We calculate the first EOF of CON and define regions for a dipole based on this pattern (shown in
195 Fig 3a for Tsub, and Table 1). We use these fixed regions to calculate timeseries for each experi-
196 ment since the EOF assumes that the whole timeseries is already known. However we have also
197 calculated the first principal component (PC1) timeseries associated with each experiment's own
198 first EOF (not shown). In experiments where there is a strong trend (1PC and hosing experiments),
199 the first EOF would show a trend, however the EOF of detrended timeseries do not resemble the
200 AMOC. In experiments where there is no or little overall trend (CON and experiments where the
201 AMOC recovers after hosing), PC1 resembles the timeseries calculated from the fixed regions.
202 We choose to use fixed regions to calculate timeseries since, in practice, the EOF analysis could
203 only be done on years prior to the year in consideration, and this restricts the time periods we can
204 examine.

205 We do not see strong instantaneous relationships of Tsub and uohc with the AMOC, other than
206 in the 1PC run (Table 2). The lack of a relationship in the control may again be because a lagged
207 relationship is more appropriate, however it is possible that changes in heat advection through gyre
208 advection also play a significant role in the relationship between temperature and AMOC (Roberts
209 et al. 2013a)). The AMOC variability in this model is also weaker than observed, which could

210 lead to an underestimation of the relationship with Atlantic ocean temperature (Yan et al. 2018).
211 We note that a dipole between the two regions used for Tsub and uohc does develop in the 1PC
212 run leading to positive correlations of this index with the AMOC, however in the hosing runs the
213 correlations are weak (Table 2).

214 *c. Density metrics*

215 The second most common class of metrics is those based on density gradients. This origi-
216 nates from the knowledge that the AMOC can be related to zonal pressure difference, and studies
217 have found that this results in an relationship between the AMOC and both meridional density
218 gradients (Thorpe et al. 2001; De Boer et al. 2010; Robson et al. 2013) and zonal density gra-
219 dients (Baehr et al. 2007). Roberts et al. (2013a) proposed a meridional difference (m.dipole)
220 and Baehr et al. (2007); Robson et al. (2016) proposed zonal density differences at different lat-
221 itudes (z.dipole, 26N.dipole). Since the density signal is mostly found in the western subpolar
222 gyre, Roberts et al. (2013a); Hermanson et al. (2014) also suggested densities in the Labrador Sea
223 (LS_mid,LS_dipole). Previous modelling studies have shown that densities in the western subpo-
224 lar gyre can be modified by surface fluxes over decadal timescales, with density anomalies then
225 propagating southwards along the western boundary (Ba et al. 2014; Buckley and Marshall 2016;
226 Ortega et al. 2016). Hence density changes in the subpolar gyre could be precursors to AMOC
227 change.

228 Of the density metrics the one that works the best is m.dipole (which we note was designed
229 for this ensemble; Jackson and Wood (2018b)). The timeseries for m.dipole is shown in Fig 7.
230 Examination of the other density metrics (not shown) shows that the differences during the hosing
231 experiments were mainly due to the lack (for LS_mid) or location (for LS_density, z.dipole) of a
232 second region to create a density gradient. For these experiments the changes in the deep ocean

233 can be very large so correcting for this correctly is important. For the density gradient at 26.5°N
234 (26N_dipole) there is little relationship with M26: the hosing experiments mostly show no change
235 or a weakening, while the 1PC experiment shows an increase. This may be because the regions
236 used to calculate the boundary densities are relatively wide and may not represent values on the
237 actual boundaries.

238 Butler et al. (2016) pointed out that, instead of density gradients, it would be more accurate of
239 use gradients in pressure itself. The meridional gradient in pressure (pintg) has a good relationship
240 with M26 across many experiments.

241 *d. Mixed Layer Depth*

242 The mixed layer depth (MLD) in March can be used as a proxy for deep convection which affects
243 the overturning circulation. Modelling studies have shown that changes in mixed layer depths can
244 occur before changes in the AMOC (Ba et al. 2014; Buckley and Marshall 2016; Ortega et al.
245 2016), so MLD may be useful for providing early warning of AMOC changes.

246 Jackson and Wood (2018a) noted that MLD may be a useful fingerprint for the AMOC in these
247 experiments. The SPG_MLD (Fig 8) and LS_MLD show largely similar behavior to the AMOC
248 timeseries with strong correlations (other than in the control, although there may be a lagged re-
249 lationship: see section 3). SPG_MLD is shown in Fig 8. The MLD timeseries shows a larger
250 interannual variability than the AMOC. It also seems to show a faster response, both in the recov-
251 ery of the MLD after hosing, and in the temporary recovery and then weakening seen in some of
252 the non-recovering experiments after hosing. In the 1PC experiment it shows a faster weakening
253 then levels off, unlike the more linear decrease of the AMOC itself. These all point to the potential
254 of the MLD to act as an early warning of the AMOC change. Since SPG_MLD shows similar,
255 but marginally better agreement with the AMOC than LS_MLD, we drop LS_MLD from further

256 analysis. We also note that the MLD in HadGEM3-GC2 is too deep in the Labrador Sea and hence
257 using a wider area is less likely to be model dependent.

258 *e. Sea level*

259 One impact of a changing AMOC is changes in sea surface heights, particularly across the Gulf
260 Stream, leading to differences in sea level along the eastern North American coast. This has led
261 to proposals of using the sea level difference between coastal locations as fingerprints (Bingham
262 and Hughes 2009; McCarthy et al. 2015a). Of the two sea level metrics, the more southerly dipole
263 (sl1) performs better than the more northerly dipole (sl0), though less well than other metrics. It
264 is possible that model deficiencies in the path of the Gulf Stream, particular in the separation from
265 the coast, could have adversely affect these metrics.

266 *f. Fresh water transports*

267 Although freshwater transports are less easy to monitor than other options, there have been sug-
268 gestions that the potential of the AMOC for collapse and the ability of the AMOC to recover may
269 be related to the transport of freshwater (de Vries and Weber 2005). As well as the more estab-
270 lished metrics related to the overturning and total freshwater transport at the southern boundary
271 of the Atlantic (fov34S, ftot34S), Jackson and Wood (2018a) found that the transports at 30°N
272 (fov30N, ftot30N) play an important role in the recovery of the hosing experiments used here.

273 Although we found good correlations of freshwater transport with the AMOC (not shown), this
274 is not surprising since we would expect a relationship with at least the overturning component of
275 the freshwater transport. We found that the freshwater transports gave no extra information, so
276 given that they are more difficult to observe, we only include them in the analysis of thresholds
277 (section 7).

278 **4. Fingerprint for variability**

279 There is evidence that the AMOC experiences decadal-multidecadal variability from model sim-
280 ulations (Zhang and Wang 2013; Ba et al. 2014) and observations of SSTs (Knight et al. 2006).
281 These changes have impacts on temperatures, precipitation and storms around the North Atlantic,
282 as well as wider impacts on monsoons. One potential use for fingerprints is in detecting these
283 changes, and potentially improving the detection time. In this model the AMOC has multidecadal
284 variability and the autocorrelation show periods of around 40-60 years (Fig 1e,f). To examine
285 how well the metrics capture the decadal-multidecadal variability of the AMOC we use running
286 decadal means (mean over the following decade starting from each year).

287 We show lagged correlations of our metrics to M26, M45 and AOHT for the control run in Fig
288 9. Correlations that are judged significant in Fig 9 are shown with solid lines, where significance
289 is tested using a moving block bootstrap with blocks of 20 years to account for autocorrelation
290 (Wilks 1997). Using longer blocks (30 years) makes little difference, but using a single year was
291 found to increase the number of values found to be significant since autocorrelation is not correctly
292 accounted for. Those metrics with no significant signal are not shown. Some metrics where the
293 results are very similar to others are also not shown, though the similarity is noted in the text. The
294 AMOC in this model has internal variability of around 30 years, leading to peaks in correlations
295 30 years before or after.

296 RAPID and OSNAP both show strong correlations near lag zero with M26, M45 and AOHT.
297 There is also a significant correlation of the upper mid ocean component of RAPID. The maximum
298 correlation of OSNAP occurs 1-2 years before the maximum correlation in RAPID in each case,
299 with RAPID coinciding with M26 but lagging M45 by a year. These lags are consistent with a
300 signal propagating southwards, however the lag is more consistent with a fast wave signal rather

301 than a slower advective signal (Buckley and Marshall 2016). Negative correlations at ± 20 -30
302 years are indications of multidecadal variability of the AMOC.

303 Of the temperature-related metrics, amv1 (and amv2 similarly but less significantly, not shown)
304 shows good correlations with M26, M45 and AOHT at lag zero, with strong lagged correlations
305 also from SST_spg. A lagged signal might be expected from an influence of the AMOC on heat
306 transport and hence on the temperatures. Reasons for signals to precede an AMOC change, such
307 as for SST_dipole, are less clear. A negative correlation preceding the AMOC could be from a
308 cold and dense anomaly that drives an AMOC change. Spatial correlations of SST (Fig 3b) shows
309 the typical horseshoe pattern of warm SSTs in the subpolar gyre, the eastern subtropics and across
310 the tropics (Ba et al. 2014; Wills et al. 2019). This is captured by those metrics that use a large
311 region covering the subpolar gyre or much of North Atlantic. The metrics focusing on a dipole
312 between the subpolar gyre and the Gulf Stream (Tsub, SST_caesar) perform less well since there
313 is no opposing temperature change in the Gulf Stream such as seen in Zhang (2008); Zhang and
314 Zhang (2015).

315 The density metrics m_dipole, LS_dipole and pintg all have significant correlations with M26,
316 M45 and AOHT. The signal in LS_dipole occurs the earliest (about 5 years before M26 and AOHT,
317 and 3 years before M45). The different lags and relationships suggest that the nature of the rela-
318 tionship between the AMOC and the Labrador Sea density depends on the depth and exact region
319 used for the density. SPG_MLD (and LS_MLD, not shown) shows significant correlations near
320 zero lag with M45 but not M26. There are also significant correlations with both sea level metrics,
321 however these are mostly lagging the changes in AMOC and AOHT. We note opposing correlation
322 signs between sl0 and sl1 suggesting that the region affected is around 40°N which is the northerly
323 region for sl0 and the southerly region for sl1.

324 There are several density and temperature metrics that are useful for monitoring AMOC vari-
325 ability, such as SST_dipole, amv1, amv2, SST_spg, LS_dipole, m_dipole, pintg. Density metrics
326 such as LS_dipole can give warning of AMOC changes up to 5 years ahead. Temperature changes
327 can also give early warning: several temperature metrics show a negative correlation (cold SSTs
328 before an AMOC increase) preceding M45. However we note that this is not true for M26 and
329 that the negative correlation is likely related to the multidecadal variability of the AMOC. Since
330 the timing and mechanisms of multidecadal variability varies a lot across models (Ba et al. 2014),
331 these negative correlations are likely to be model dependent. One advantage of SST metrics is the
332 potential of extending the historical record back in time to understand past variability (Rahmstorf
333 et al. 2015; Caesar et al. 2018).

334 **5. Detecting a weakening**

335 Most metrics shown in Table 2 are able to detect a weakening in a 1% or hosing scenario,
336 however a metric that is good for detection and early warning will detect a change earlier. This
337 may be because the change actually happens earlier, or because there is a greater signal-to-noise
338 ratio, meaning that the signal emerges from the noise earlier. Using the hosing experiments and
339 the 1PC experiment we use annual means to calculate the earliest year Y where the trend (from
340 the start of the experiment to year Y) of the forced experiment is outside the 95% percentile of
341 the trends of the control experiment of length Y years (Baehr et al. 2007; Brennan et al. 2008;
342 Roberts and Palmer 2012). We also calculate a signal-to-noise ratio for each metric ($s2n$), based
343 on the ratio of the standard deviation of all weakening experiments to the standard deviation in the
344 control.

345 Results are shown in Table 3 for M26, M45, AOHT, the observational arrays (RAPID, OSNAP),
346 and those metrics where the detection time is shorter in most experiments than for M26. There

347 are some differences between metrics, however it is difficult to assess whether those differences
348 are significant or simply due to internal variability without having ensembles for each forcing
349 scenario. There is mostly a faster detection time for M26 than either M45 or AOHT. This may
350 be because of a greater signal-to-noise. We note that OSNAP has a number of experiments where
351 the detection time is faster than M26, despite having a similar signal-to-noise ratio. This may be
352 because changes in the AMOC are initiated at high latitudes, and can take a few years to reach the
353 subtropics (Buckley and Marshall 2016).

354 A few metrics show mostly faster detection times (though not in every experiment) than M26. In
355 particular *m_dipole* has detection times that are at least 30% faster than the AMOC itself for all the
356 hosing experiments, though detection is slower in the 1PC run. This may be because temperature
357 increase from the increased greenhouse gases also affect the densities used for the fingerprint.
358 *LS_dipole* also has earlier or equal detection times for all experiments. We note that these metrics
359 both have higher signal-to-noise ratios than M26, which could also improve the detection time.
360 The *SPG_MLD* also has mostly earlier detection times despite a similar signal-to-noise ratio. The
361 good detection times of these metrics (*m_dipole*, *LS_dipole* and *SPG_MLD*) may also be because
362 they are monitoring processes occurring at higher latitudes where the signal can precede M26.

363 No single metric shows a consistent improvement over M26 itself, however several show de-
364 tection rates that are similar or better in most experiments. These suggest that monitoring of the
365 subpolar gyre region, in particular the densities, deep convection and overturning, could provide
366 early warning for changes.

367 **6. Detecting recovery**

368 The last section discussed the time of detection for an ongoing weakening, however there are
369 many experiments where hosing is removed and the AMOC either recovers or stays weak. A

370 simple time of detection of a trend from the start of the experiment does not distinguish between
371 a metric which starts changing but takes some time to emerge from the noise, and a metric where
372 the change is delayed. One good example of this is the experiment where the AMOC recovers
373 after 150 year of 0.1 Sv hosing (Fig 2, purple), where the recovery does not actually start until 100
374 years after the removal of hosing.

375 An alternative method for assessing the time of detection is presented here. Assuming a window
376 of length n years, we calculate trends of length n for the experiments where the AMOC recovers
377 after hosing and compare to a bootstrapped probability density function (pdf) of trends of length n
378 years from the control. The time at which the trends are below the 5% of the pdf are a detection of
379 a negative trend and above the 95% are a detection of a positive trend. We choose $n=20$ years as a
380 balance between a period which is too short (where an ongoing signal is difficult to detect because
381 of variability) and too long (where detection of changes at the start of the run are delayed). We
382 divide the recovery experiments into those where the AMOC recovers and those where it does not
383 and assess the times of the first detected positive and negative trends in the two groups.

384 Since there is only one of the recovery experiments (off10_10) where a negative AMOC change
385 is detected (an AMOC non-recovery is normally associated with a relatively flat timeseries), we
386 focus on the positive trends and ask whether any metrics can detect the increase before the AMOC
387 timeseries itself. Fig 10 shows the difference between the detected time of increase for each metric
388 from the detected time of increase for M26. Only metrics which perform similarly, or better than
389 M26 are shown. We note that off01_150 in particular shows a wide range of detection times. From
390 examination of the timeseries (Fig 2) we can see that the AMOC recovery is initially slow with a
391 weak signal compared to the noise (interannual variability). This long time period increases the
392 likelihood of falsely detecting a recovery, and the large noise compared to the signal results in a

393 large spread of detection times. We note that using an initial condition ensemble would reduce the
394 uncertainty on the detection times.

395 For most experiments where the AMOC recovers (left side of plot), there is a faster or similar
396 detection rate of recovery from `m_dipole` and `LS_dipole` than the AMOC timeseries itself in all
397 experiments. `SPG_MLD` also performs well with most experiments having a similar or earlier
398 detection time than M26.

399 One aspect of the AMOC behavior once hosing has been removed in these experiments, is that
400 the AMOC can temporarily strengthen, before weakening and continuing in a weaker state (Fig
401 2). Because of this behavior, positive trends can be detected in M26 in those experiments where
402 the AMOC does not recover (Fig 10, right hand side), giving a false indication that the AMOC
403 will continue recovering.

404 We can assess these metrics to understand whether they can indicate whether the AMOC is
405 going to recover or remain in a quasi-stable weak state. For a good indicator of recovery after
406 hosing, the metric should have high detection rate of recovery and a low false detection rate. The
407 time of detection should also be as small as possible. Table 4 shows detection rates of recovery
408 trends (see also Fig 10). Most metrics have a high detection rate of recovery, and `m_dipole` has
409 the fastest detection rate. However it also has a high false detection rate since all the runs where
410 the AMOC does not recover do show an initial increase in `m_dipole`. Other metrics also have high
411 false detection rates, including M26 timeseries itself. Three metrics have low false detection rates:
412 `LSmid`, `pintg` and `SPG_MLD`, and of these the latter has the fastest detection rate of recovery.
413 Hence `SPG_MLD` is able to quickly determine whether the AMOC is recovering or not.

414 Examination of the timeseries of `SPG_MLD` (Fig 8) shows that there is some temporary increase
415 indicating increased convection, however it is short lived and mostly within the large variability
416 exhibited in the control. Hence the strengthening is not detected.

417 Hence we find that SPG_MLD is quick to detect recovery of the AMOC and produces a low false
418 detection rate. However detecting the lack of recovery is difficult because it requires detecting no
419 trend.

420 **7. Detecting a threshold**

421 Jackson and Wood (2018a) showed that the AMOC in these experiments experiences hysteresis:
422 when the hosing stops, in some experiments the AMOC does not recover (also see Fig 2. They
423 show that how long the hosing is experienced is important and that the AMOC has temporary
424 resilience. So with a hosing strength of 0.3 Sv (hos03), after 20 years of hosing the AMOC can
425 recover, but not after 50 years of hosing. Hence the threshold of temporary resilience is crossed
426 between 20 and 50 years in this case, giving us a window for the threshold. They found that the
427 AMOC strength was a good indicator of this threshold, with experiments where the AMOC does
428 not weaken below 8 Sv showing a subsequent recovery once hosing stops, but those where the
429 AMOC weakened below 8 Sv stayed in a weak state. They also found that salt or freshwater trans-
430 port by the AMOC at 30°N, and mixed layer depth in the Labrador sea were potential indicators.
431 However that analysis used centered decadal means to remove noise, but this means that after eg
432 20 years of hosing you need to know the AMOC averaged from year 15-25. For a better indicator
433 we need to consider the preceding decade (ie years 10-20).

434 Fig 11 uses decadal means from the preceding decade for different metrics. Metrics not shown
435 are RAPID and OSNAP which show similar results to M26, and metrics which have large overlaps
436 between the bars. The blue bars show the range of values for the periods before and including the
437 lower bound of the threshold (ie where the AMOC can recover when hosing stops) and the red bars
438 show the range of values for the periods after and including the upper bound of the threshold (ie
439 where the AMOC does not recover when hosing stops). The majority of metrics show a separation

440 between the two ranges when using a centered decadal mean (not shown), however when using the
441 previous decade only SST_dipole and LS_dipole show a separation. This means that the strength
442 of these indicators can be used (in these experiments) for determining whether the threshold has
443 been crossed.

444 One interesting observation is that fov34S is not a useful indicator of crossing this threshold. The
445 freshwater transport by the AMOC into the Atlantic has been proposed by many studies to be an
446 indicator of whether an AMOC off state exists, and hence whether hysteresis can occur (de Vries
447 and Weber 2005; Huisman et al. 2010; Drijfhout et al. 2011). These theories are based on the
448 idea that if $fov34S < 0$ then a feedback occurs: weakening AMOC results in less export of fresh
449 water from the Atlantic, resulting in a fresher, more buoyant Atlantic and greater weakening of
450 the AMOC. However Jackson and Wood (2018a) showed that this feedback did not occur in these
451 experiments, since the Atlantic as a whole did not necessarily get fresher. Instead the freshwater
452 transport at $30^{\circ}N$ (fov30N) was found to be more relevant with the subpolar North Atlantic getting
453 fresher. The metric fov34S does not give any indication of crossing the threshold, and fov30N is
454 not as clear an indicator as SST_dipole and LS_dipole (Fig 11).

455 SST_dipole and LS_dipole give the clearest indications of crossing the threshold, however a key
456 caveat is that we do not know what the values of these thresholds would be in the real ocean, or
457 even whether the same hysteresis behavior is seen.

458 **8. Conclusions**

459 We use a suite of experiments to examine different methods proposed in other studies for mon-
460 itoring the AMOC. This includes model representations of the current AMOC monitoring arrays
461 for the RAPID section (at $26.5^{\circ}N$) and the OSNAP section ($50-60^{\circ}N$). These arrays show strong
462 relationships with the true model AMOC at $26.5^{\circ}N$ and $45^{\circ}N$ and the ocean heat transports. We

463 also examine various metrics based on aspects such as ocean temperature, density, sea level and
464 mixed layer depth that have been proposed as potential fingerprints (representing an important
465 aspect of the AMOC).

466 Temperature metrics based on large scale temperature patterns are found to be good fingerprints
467 for AMOC variability, but less so for long-term AMOC weakening where patterns can be different
468 in different scenarios and changes take longer to detect than other metrics. However a dipole in
469 SST between the subpolar gyre and the south Atlantic (SST_dipole) is good at giving early warning
470 of passing a threshold in this model beyond which the AMOC doesn't recover. Temperature
471 metrics based on local patterns are not found to be useful fingerprints in any scenario.

472 Density metrics prove to be useful fingerprints for a range of scenarios. In particular the large
473 scale meridional density gradient and the vertical gradient of density in the Labrador sea are good
474 fingerprints for both assessing AMOC variability (with the Labrador sea density giving a 5 year
475 early warning of AMOC change) and for detecting AMOC changes. The Labrador sea density can
476 also give early warning of passing a threshold beyond which the AMOC doesn't recover.

477 In some hosing experiments the AMOC experiences a temporary recovery before reducing again
478 to a weak state. A number of the metrics replicate (or exaggerate) this temporary recovery, however
479 the mixed layer depth is a useful metric because it quickly distinguishes those experiments where
480 the AMOC recovers from those where the AMOC stays in a weak state after a temporary recovery.

481 Of course this analysis has all been conducted with one climate model, and there are likely to be
482 differences in other models (Roberts et al. 2013a). In particular we note that there are differences in
483 the mechanisms and in the frequency of AMOC variability across models (Ba et al. 2014; Menary
484 et al. 2015) which are likely to impact on the patterns associated with variability. It is also possible
485 that modifications to the metrics here (which have mostly been developed using a single model)
486 could make them more successful. However understanding how these proposed metrics perform

487 in one model across a number of scenarios is a first step to developing a robust fingerprint. We also
488 need to improve our understanding of the processes involved and hence which metrics are most
489 likely to be robust.

490 Current arrays monitoring the AMOC directly (RAPID and OSNAP) are shown to perform
491 well, though fingerprints can provide added values. Results here show that some metrics are useful
492 fingerprints, however the best metric may depend on the question being asked. The results do point
493 to continued monitoring of densities, surface temperatures and mixed layer depths, particularly in
494 the subpolar gyre. A successful monitoring strategy for climate-relevant AMOC changes is likely
495 to involve using multiple fingerprints and physical understanding.

496 *Data availability.* The processed data used for this study are available from
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671 **LIST OF TABLES**

672 **Table 1.** List of metrics used 33

673 **Table 2.** Correlations with decadal mean AMOC at 26.5°N with metrics for the con-
674 trol, 1PC, hosing and recovery experiments. Hosing and recovery values are
675 means of correlations across the different experiments. Bold values are where
676 the correlations are significant ($p < 0.05$). The final column is the number of
677 experiments (out of 21) where there is a significant correlation. 34

678 **Table 3.** Year to detect a change (trend is outside 95% of control trends) for each ex-
679 periment. Second last column (N) is the number of experiments where the
680 detection time is less than for M26. Final column ($s2n$) is the average signal
681 to noise, defined as the mean standard deviation of all weakening experiments
682 divided by the standard deviation of the control. 35

683 **Table 4.** Statistics of trends for metrics where at least 75% of experiments where the
684 AMOC recovers have positive trends detected. For those experiments where the
685 AMOC recovers (does not recover) the statistics show the mean and standard
686 deviation of the years to detect a trend in each metric, and the percentage of
687 experiments where the trend is detected. 36

TABLE 1. List of metrics used

Metric name	region/method	reference
RAPID.MOC	AMOC strength at RAPID section	McCarthy et al. (2015b); Roberts et al. (2013b)
RAPID.UMO	Upper mid ocean strength at RAPID section	McCarthy et al. (2015b); Roberts et al. (2013b)
RAPID.FC	Florida Current strength at RAPID section	McCarthy et al. (2015b); Roberts et al. (2013b)
OSNAP	AMOC strength at OSNAP section	Lozier et al. (2019)
SST.dipole	45-80°N, 70°W-30°E minus 0-45°S, 70°W-30°E	Roberts et al. (2013a)
SST.caesar	dipole over masked regions with Nov-May mean SST	Caesar et al. (2018)
SST.spg	spg region (as SST.caesar) minus N hemisphere mean SST	Rahmstorf et al. (2015)
amv1	0-60°N, 50°W-10°E minus global mean	Msadek et al. (2010)
amv2	40-60°N, 50°W-10°E minus global mean	Msadek et al. (2010); Latif et al. (2004)
Tsub	47-60°N, 15-25°W, 400m minus 37-43°N, 50-70°W, 400m	Zhang (2008); Zhang and Zhang (2015)
uohc	43-53°N, 45-55°W, 0-700m minus 37-43°N, 50-70°W, 0-700m	Zhang (2008); Zhang and Zhang (2015)
26N.dipole	70-80°W, 1700-3100m minus 26-36°W, 1700-3100m at 26°N	Baehr et al. (2007)
LS.dipole	45-80°N, 45-70°W, 0-800m minus 45-80°N, 45-70°W, 800-1800m	Roberts et al. (2013a)
m.dipole	45-65°N, 0-70°W, FD minus 0-45°S, 70°W-30°E, FD	Roberts et al. (2013a)
z.dipole	35-66°N, 30-75°W, FD minus 35-66°N, 0-25°W, FD	Hermanson et al. (2014)
pintg	45-55°N, 45-60°W minus 25-35°S, 40-55°W	Butler et al. (2016); Haskins et al. (2019)
LS.mld	maximum of March MLD over the Labrador Sea (53-65°N, 47.7-62°W)	Jackson and Wood (2018a)
SPG.mld	maximum of March MLD over the subpolar gyre (50-79°N, 68°W-17°E)	Jackson and Wood (2018a)
sl0	value at 40.6°N (near coast) minus that at 43.8°N (near coast)	Bingham and Hughes (2009)
sl1	26-34°N, near coast minus 36.5-42°N, near coast	McCarthy et al. (2015a)
fov34S	FW transport by overturning at 34°S in Atlantic	de Vries and Weber (2005)
ftot34S	FW transport by overturning+gyre at 34°S in Atlantic	de Vries and Weber (2005)
fov30N	FW transport by overturning at 30°N in Atlantic	Mecking et al. (2016); Jackson and Wood (2018a)
ftot30N	FW transport by overturning+gyre at 30°N in Atlantic	Mecking et al. (2016); Jackson and Wood (2018a)

688 TABLE 2. Correlations with decadal mean AMOC at 26.5°N with metrics for the control, 1PC, hosing and
689 recovery experiments. Hosing and recovery values are means of correlations across the different experiments.
690 Bold values are where the correlations are significant ($p < 0.05$). The final column is the number of experiments
691 (out of 21) where there is a significant correlation.

	con	1PC	hos	recovery	N:p < 0.05
RAPID	0.99	1.00	0.99	0.98	21
RAPID.FC	0.52	0.97	0.96	0.87	21
RAPID_UMO	0.25	-0.44	-0.21	0.32	11
OSNAP	0.86	0.98	0.96	0.87	19
SST_dipole	0.37	-0.82	0.91	0.52	15
SST_caesar	0.18	0.87	0.90	0.49	13
SST_spg	0.53	0.96	0.87	0.64	16
amv1	0.65	0.50	0.98	0.77	17
amv2	0.56	0.95	0.94	0.70	18
Tsub	0.32	0.95	0.22	0.57	11
uohc	0.09	0.67	-0.61	0.29	8
LS_mid	0.30	0.96	0.87	0.40	12
LS_dipole	0.37	0.99	0.98	0.66	16
m_dipole	0.74	0.96	0.98	0.80	18
z_dipole	-0.40	0.96	0.94	0.57	15
26N_dipole	0.22	-0.91	-0.16	-0.26	8
pintg	0.56	0.98	0.94	0.66	15
LS_mld	0.39	0.97	0.87	0.83	19
SPG_mld	0.44	0.97	0.95	0.84	19
sl0	-0.15	0.66	0.32	0.04	4
sl1	0.12	0.92	0.74	0.45	10

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693 column (N) is the number of experiments where the detection time is less than for M26. Final column ($s2n$) is
694 the average signal to noise, defined as the mean standard deviation of all weakening experiments divided by the
695 standard deviation of the control.

	hos01	hos02	hos03	hos05	hos10	1PC	N	s2n
M26	30	7	5	7	7	34		3.0
M45	39	13	10	5	9	25	2	2.2
AOHT	30	10	8	13	7	38	0	2.2
RAPID	29	12	10	12	7	32	2	2.9
OSNAP	24	10	8	5	5	27	4	2.9
m_dipole	21	3	3	3	3	44	5	11.6
LS_dipole	18	7	3	2	2	29	5	9.6
SPG_MLD	28	7	7	5	3	32	4	3.2

696 TABLE 4. Statistics of trends for metrics where at least 75% of experiments where the AMOC recovers have
697 positive trends detected. For those experiments where the AMOC recovers (does not recover) the statistics show
698 the mean and standard deviation of the years to detect a trend in each metric, and the percentage of experiments
699 where the trend is detected.

	positive trend when recovering			positive trend when not recovering		
	mean	std	percent	mean	std	percent
M26	26	9	75	33	10	57
RAPID	36	28	75	24	1	71
OSNAP	41	34	100	22	0	29
SST_dipole	26	7	88	31	23	86
amv1	30	17	88	32	28	86
amv2	36	19	100	22	3	86
LS_dipole	21	1	100	20	0	100
z_dipole	29	10	88	26	7	100
m_dipole	20	0	100	20	0	100
pintg	61	25	100	20	0	14
SPG_MLD	26	8	100	18	0	14

700 **LIST OF FIGURES**

701 **Fig. 1.** a) Mean AMOC streamfunction in CON (Sv). b) AMOC streamfunction in last decade
702 of hos02 (Sv). c) AMOC streamfunction in last decade of IPC (Sv). d) Atlantic ocean
703 heat transport by latitude for the control (solid), and last decades of IPC (grey) and hos02
704 (dashed). e) Timeseries of M26 (black), M45 (red) and AOHT (blue, multiplied by a factor
705 of 10) in the control with a running decadal mean. f) Lagged correlations of running decadal
706 means of M26 with M26 (ie autocorrelation), M45 and AOHT. 38

707 **Fig. 2.** Timeseries of M26 for CON (black) and various amounts of hosing (see panel titles) in gray,
708 with experiment where hosing is stopped (after 10 (blue), 20 (green), 30 (cyan), 40 (yellow),
709 50 (red), 100 (magenta) and 150 (purple) years) are shown in colors. The final panel shows
710 the IPC experiment in blue. 39

711 **Fig. 3.** Temperature metrics. a) First EOF over region shown of 400m temperature in HadGEM3-
712 GC2. Also shown are the regions used for Tsub (black boxes) b) Correlation of decadal
713 mean SST and M26. Also shown are regions used for amv1 (black dashed box) and amv2
714 (gray box). c) Difference between SST at the end of the IPC run from the control. Also
715 shown are the regions used for SST_caesar and SST_spg. d) Difference between SST at the
716 end of the hos02 run from the control. Also shown are the boxes used for SST_dipole. 40

717 **Fig. 4.** Other metrics. a) Lines show the locations of M26 and RAPID (magenta), M45 (blue),
718 the latitude of the maximum of the time mean ocean heat transport (green), OSNAP (red),
719 Fov30N (cyan) and Fov34S (yellow). Also shown are the regions to calculate LS_mld (grey)
720 and SPG_mld (dashed black). b) Regions used to calculate dipoles of sea level for sl0 (red)
721 and sl1 (blue). c) Regions used to calculate LS_dipole (red) and 26N_dipole (blue). d)
722 Regions used to calculate z_dipole (red) and m_dipole (blue). Details of metrics are given in
723 Table 1. 41

724 **Fig. 5.** As Fig 2 but for amv2 42

725 **Fig. 6.** As Fig 2 but for SST_dipole 43

726 **Fig. 7.** As Fig 2 but for m_dipole 44

727 **Fig. 8.** As Fig 2 but for SPG_MLD 45

728 **Fig. 9.** Lagged corr of M26 (top), M45 (middle) and AOHT (bottom) running decadal means with
729 various metrics (see legends). Negative lags means the metrics precede, and positive means
730 the metrics follow the AMOC/AOHT. Solid lines are where the correlation is significant (see
731 text). 46

732 **Fig. 10.** Difference between detection times of 10 year trends from those for M26. Shown are obser-
733 vational metrics (RAPID and OSNAP), and potential fingerprints where detection times are
734 faster than M26 in most experiments. Note that amv1 is similar to amv2 and not shown. 47

735 **Fig. 11.** Values of various metrics (labeled) during the hosing experiments. Blue bars show the range
736 of decadal means for time periods before the threshold is reached and red bars show the
737 range of decadal means for time periods after the threshold is reached. Eg for hos05 the
738 AMOC recovers after up to 20 years of hosing, so decadal means of values before year 20
739 are before the threshold. After 50 years of hosing the AMOC does not recover, so decadal
740 means of values past this point (including years 41-50) are considered past the threshold.
741 The black dashed line shows the mean between the extrema of the two bars. 48

742 FIG. 1. a) Mean AMOC streamfunction in CON (Sv). b) AMOC streamfunction in last decade of hos02 (Sv).
 743 c) AMOC streamfunction in last decade of 1PC (Sv). d) Atlantic ocean heat transport by latitude for the control
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 754 SST at the end of the hos02 run from the control. Also shown are the boxes used for SST_dipole.

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FIG. 8. As Fig 2 but for SPG_MLD

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